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***Propaganda: Study of the evolution of impact and modern methods in the
realities of the Russian media***

The study of propaganda matters in the scientific and academic fields because it helps to understand how communities shape their views, how manipulation and distortion of information can influence public opinion and decision-making. Many researchers and scholars have devoted their work to the analysis of propaganda and its impact on public consciousness: Edward Bernays, Jacques Ellul, Noam Chomsky, Daniel Lerner, Elizabeth Noelle-Neumann.

Facts are used to convince people of their position, but what if the facts speak against them? Then the propaganda is used. This word sounds the same in most European languages, it came from the name of the organization "Congregatio de propaganda fide" (Congregation for the Spread of Faith) [2]. Until the 20th century, propaganda meant the spread of religious faith. Then the main tool was the printing press: with the help of books and leaflets, Martin Luther shattered the influence of the Catholic Church, turning half of Europe into Protestantism. [3]

It should be noted that propaganda techniques are thousands, but we will consider the most basic of them.

I. Divisions and Conflict

Propaganda clearly divides the world into black and white, good and evil, friends and foes. For example, take a quote from Russian propagandist Dmitry Kisilev: "Russia today is a kind of island of normalcy, if you look at the Western drunkard... We are different".

The division into the "friend or foe" works because our brain saves effort. No propaganda calls itself invaders and occupiers, the image of the enemy is symmetrical on all sides. [1]

II. Newspeak

Philosophers say: "Language shapes thinking". The words, the concepts, the terms we use affect how we relate to people and events.

Imagine that for many years you have been told: «War is peace, freedom is slavery, ignorance is power». This is a fragment from the famous anti-utopia «1984», there the word «newspeak» is first found. [4]

And here is what Federation Councillor Elena Mizulina says: “Prohibition as a rule of law from which the law is constructed is the greatest freedom of man. The prohibition is where the person is free”.

III. The False Dilemma

The propagandists have another trick near the newspeak - a false dilemma. People are asked to choose the lesser of two evils, where one option is advantageous to power, the other is obviously terrible.

Before the vote on the amendments to the Russian constitution, russian propaganda showed a commercial where a gay couple adopts a child and asked a question: “You will choose this Russia? No? Then vote for the amendments”.

This, too, is a false dilemma - either vote for the amendments, or the whole country will become like that. It is understood that there is absolutely no link between these allegations. In addition, same-sex couples were prohibited from adopting children in Russia even before the amendments.

IV. The illusion of majority and reference to authority

To legitimize its words, propaganda must show that the masses support it. This is done through interviews with ordinary people and surveys. The largest independent polling center «Levada» in Russia was declared a foreign agent. Thus, the state wants to leave the monopoly on social questions. In the Internet era, bots were added, channels that specifically set their audience on specific posts to create the illusion of the majority. The aim of these mechanisms is for people to see the predominance of the majority and to stop resisting it. People tend to join the majority and do not want to be a rogue. This is called «conformism».

V. Totalitarianism

The next approach means total control over the lives of citizens. First, totalitarianism is expressed through censorship. The goal of censorship is unanimity. Every month in Russia there are fewer and fewer sources of information that would broadcast information different from that shown on TV. In the absence of alternatives, a person begins to believe a common opinion. Second, totalitarianism in the decisions. Every decision is presented as the only correct, as no other is given. And the last approach - repeating. If you repeat something 1,000 times, both the audience and the propagandist will surely believe it. [5]

We have listed only part of the propaganda techniques. At the moment we do not have simple and clear instructions on how to confront it, except one. The questions are the most effective weapon against propaganda. “On what is it based?”, “Where are the statistics?”, “Who is this expert?”, and “What do other people and alternative sources of information say about it?”.

Comprehensive approaches and efforts are needed to counter propaganda and its negative effects. An important step is the development of information literacy and critical thinking among the population so that people can consciously analyse and evaluate the information received.

1. Yanko Tsvetkov Atlas of stereotypes and prejudices
https://f.ua/statik/files/products/515946/atlas-stereotipov-i-predrassudkov-9785916712681_8265.pdf
2. Edward Bernays "Propaganda" (1928)